

Annual Report

2024

SND

Swedish National Data Service

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Preface

2024 has been an active year for the Swedish National Data Service (SND). A major focus has been the continued development of the national web portal [Researchdata.se](https://researchdata.se), where you can find, share, and reuse research data from many fields. As our largest deliverable, the portal is an effort to achieve the goal from the EU and the Swedish government of open access to publicly funded research data. By 2026, and it will launch in early 2025. Simultaneously, we have worked on transforming snd.se into a website tailored to research data support staff and the general public. Two separate websites will provide greater clarity for our designated communities.

This year also saw the launch of the one-year KAFFE project, mapping researchers' data-related practices and needs in relation to existing e-infrastructures. The project will inform how the Swedish e-infrastructure landscape can evolve to better meet future needs. While not a deliverable in SND's application for the current funding period, it responds to urgent needs identified by the SND Network and Consortium.

In parallel, the Swedish Research Council has been tasked by the government to propose how national e-infrastructure for research can be developed through coordination and organizational change, with results due in June 2025.

In May, the Swedish Research Council extended SND's current funding period by two years, during which SND will undergo an external evaluation. We welcome this process, as the current e-infrastructure landscape

is highly fragmented, and SND support all steps towards greater coherence.

SND has also strengthened international collaboration, not least through our growing involvement in EOSC as a member of the EOSC Association.

Members of the SND Network have once again shown strong commitment by engaging in events and working groups. The SND Network is an indispensable part of our common infrastructure.

A highlight of the year was a joint meeting in Stockholm with the SND Steering Committee, Consortium Advisory Council, and DAU Council, which participants suggested should become an annual tradition.

Finally, I would like to acknowledge my predecessor, Max Petzold, who left SND in 2023 to become Deputy Vice-Chancellor for Digitalization and Knowledge Transfer at the University of Gothenburg. I want to express my sincere gratitude for his efforts in shaping SND into the strong, respected organization it is

today – an integral part of Sweden's e-infrastructure landscape. My ambition is to keep the flag flying high and further strengthen SND's role as a key actor in the evolving landscape of research data.

Eva Stensköld

Director

SND Network

2024 has been an active year for the SND Network. SND has organized a variety of webinars, digital Q&A sessions, workshops, and in-person events. The two in-person network meetings, in Gothenburg in spring and in Stockholm in autumn, were highly appreciated, with around 100 participants each. In collaboration with KTH Royal Institute of Technology, SND has also organized a one-day conference on research data from artistic research, which was well received.

Several of the working groups in the SND Network have been active and generated valuable resources and deliverables. Staff from the SND main office have also visited several of the member organizations of the SND Network to discuss the practical work in managing and sharing research data.

Members of the SND Network

At the end of 2024, the SND Network consisted of the following member organizations (Consortium organizations in bold text).

1. Blekinge Institute of Technology
2. **Chalmers University of Technology**
3. Dalarna University
4. Halmstad University
5. Jönköping University
6. Karlstad University
7. **Karolinska Institutet**
8. Kristianstad University
9. **KTH Royal Institute of Technology**
10. Linköping University
11. Linnaeus University
12. Luleå University of Technology
13. **Lund University**
14. Malmö University
15. Mid Sweden University
16. Mälardalen University
17. Swedish Veterinary Agency
18. RISE Research Institutes of Sweden
19. Royal College of Music
20. Sophiahemmet University
21. Stockholm School of Economics
22. **Stockholm University**
23. Swedish Defence University
24. Swedish Geotechnical Institute
25. Swedish Polar Research Secretariat
26. **Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences**
27. Södertörn University
28. Swedish School of Sport and Health Sciences
29. **Umeå University**
30. University College Stockholm
31. University of Borås
32. **University of Gothenburg**
33. University of Gävle
34. University of Skövde
35. University West
36. **Uppsala University**
37. Örebro University

Network activities

Full-day meetings and conferences

SND network meeting in Gothenburg

Themes: Open science and Information security within research data.

A day on artistic research data

A one-day conference at KTH, highlighting and exploring key issues related to research data in practice-based and artistic research.

SND network meeting in Stockholm

Theme: "Research data – from seed to loaf"; roles and responsibilities related to the research data process and SND's coordinating function in the research data landscape.

Webinars

Information security at higher education institutions

A presentation of the Swedish National Audit Office's audit report from 2023.

Nordic webinar series

Policy and practice in the development of open science – Finland. Speakers from CSC, the Finnish Social Science Data Archive, the National Coordination for Open Science and Research in Finland, and University of Helsinki.

Managing and sharing interview data

Different perspectives on how to manage and share qualitative interview data, with presenters at SND and Umeå University.

Nordic webinar series

Policy and practice in the development of open science – Sweden. Presentations from SND, Lund University, SUHF, and the Swedish Research Council.

Qualitative data analysis software – Introduction to NVivo

Webinar for researchers on the NVivo tool for qualitative data.

EOSC Future Climate Neutral and Smart Cities Webinar

A presentation of the EOSC Future Science Project on “Climate Neutral and Smart Cities.”

SND’s flagships

Presentations of the four active Flagship Projects in the SND Consortium during 2024.

FAIR over Time

A closer look at the concept “FAIR over Time” with presenters from SND’s working group on archival matters and information management.

SND IT forum on Trusted Research Environments (TRE)

A discussion of solutions and work on secure environments for managing sensitive data with presentations from staff at the University of Gothenburg, Lund University, and Uppsala University.

EOSC – what is happening and how do Swedish actors contribute?

An update on current events in EOSC from a Swedish perspective, with speakers from SND, NBIS, SciLifeLab, Sunet, and the Swedish Research Council.

Working groups in the SND Network

SND has a variety of working groups and specialist groups within the SND Network.

Roadmap for research data activities (“Orienteringskartan”)

“Orienteringskartan” is a practical tool to guide the Swedish HEIs on the road to Open Science. The tool is updated annually; in 2024, it has been revised following a new version of the SUHF National Roadmap for Open Science. There are also a number of new examples of activities from the HEIs in their work with open science. The working group consists of members from 10–12 HEIs in the SND Network.

Terminology in research data management

This group is working with research data management terminology in Swedish, aiming to compile a Swedish glossary on key RDM terms. In 2024, the group has also advised on local and national terminology initiatives. Terminology work is a central part of the KAFFE project; the working group is part of the KAFFE project group, and the glossary development will run parallel to the project.

The Archivists’ group

The group includes archivists from HEIs in the SND Network and focuses on questions related to the archiving and long-term preservation of research data. In 2024, it has developed and presented materials under the theme “FAIR over Time.”

SND Consortium

SND is governed by a consortium consisting of nine universities: University of Gothenburg, Chalmers University of Technology, Karolinska Institutet, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Lund University, Stockholm University, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Umeå University, and Uppsala University. University of Gothenburg is the host university of SND, and the SND main office is in Gothenburg.

Steering Committee

SND's Steering Committee consists of individuals appointed based on their expertise in infrastructure and research data matters. The members of the Steering Committee are:

- **Hans Karlsson**, Professor in theoretical chemistry, Uppsala University (chair, from June 2024)
- **Björn Halleröd**, Professor in sociology, University of Gothenburg (chair until June 2024)
- **Marianne Gullberg**, Professor in psycholinguistics, Lund University
- **Sverker Holmgren**, Professor in scientific computing and Director of Chalmers e-Commons, Chalmers University of Technology
- **Vigdis Kvalheim**, Head of unit for research and knowledge resources, Sikt, Norway
- **Monica Lassi***, Senior data governance specialist, IKEA
- **Cecilia Martinsson Björkdahl**, Head of Compliance & Data Office, Karolinska Institutet
- **Johan Rung**, Head of SciLifeLab Data Centre, Uppsala University
- **Anders Wåhlin***, Associate professor and Director of Centre for Biomedical Engineering and Physics, Umeå University.

SND's Steering Committee has had four meetings in 2024, one of which was a residential meeting to facilitate more in-depth discussions. The discussions have been centered around SND's long-term development, strategy and funding, with a special focus on the application for the continued funding period 2027–2028, to be submitted in March 2025,

*= Stepped down from the Steering Committee before the end of their term due to unforeseen circumstances.

and the national investigation on how a Swedish e-infrastructure for research can be developed through coordination and organizational change.

The Consortium Advisory Council

Representatives from the nine SND Consortium universities convene with a council of stakeholders, the SND Consortium Advisory Council. The council serves as a forum for information exchange and consultation among the universities in the SND Consortium. The council advises the Steering Committee on the strategic plan, budget, and termination plan. Additionally, it provides input to the University of Gothenburg, which administers SND's funding, regarding the Steering Committee's chair and composition, as well as the appointment of SND's Director and Deputy Director. Each university in the SND Consortium appoints one representative to the council, and the chair is from the University of Gothenburg. From June 2024, Björn Halleröd, Professor in sociology, University of Gothenburg is chair of the SND Consortium Advisory Council. The council has had one meeting in 2024.

Flagships

There have been four active Flagship projects during 2024, run by members of the SND Consortium. A Flagship is a comprehensive project, limited in time, to develop routines, knowledge, and technology for research data management or data sharing. A clearly stated requirement is that other HEIs shall be able to benefit from the results.

Chalmers and KTH:

Efficient reuse of administrative research information from project initiation to data publication

The project was an independent continuation of the flagship pilot conducted by Chalmers and KTH in collaboration with SND. The goal is to reduce the administrative burden on researchers by reusing information about research projects through machine-readable data management plans that communicate with other research administrative systems. The project aims to develop a solution to create and fill out a data management plan using metadata from other systems, such as SweCris. One major benefit of the initiative is that researchers and research administrators can avoid having to manually enter the same information into multiple systems.

The project was completed by the end of 2023, but a final workshop was held during the autumn of 2024.

Karolinska Institutet:

KI Data Repository – Phase 1: Interim solution for local storage without integration with DORIS

This is a two-phase project to create a solution where researchers at KI can securely and in a structured way store sensitive data and make them accessible through the SND catalogue. In the first phase (the Flagship project), this is done manually via the interim solution for local storage without integration with SND (DORIS). Phase two will involve creating permanent local storage with an integration between the university storage and DORIS. The storage solution is a central part of the universities' efforts to make research data accessible. The results from KI's project can demonstrate how to create functional storage systems before a final integrated data storage is in place.

Lund University:

Preserved and accessible databases

This project aimed to develop a process for making databases simultaneously accessible and preserved for long-term storage. An inventory conducted at the university revealed that researchers need to safeguard the operation and maintenance of databases over a longer time, especially after the project ends and funding is uncertain. The Flagship project primarily reached out to researchers in the humanities and social sciences, but the results can be applied to other scientific fields. Questions about responsibility, operations, and costs for the preservation of research data are relevant for all Swedish HEIs. This project showed how to work towards creating long-term technical systems and solutions for preserving databases.

A concluding workshop for the project was held during autumn 2024 and the project was finalized by the end of 2024.

Stockholm University:

Certification of the Bolin Centre Database – a repository for climate, environmental, and earth system data at Stockholm University

The goal for this project is to make the Bolin Centre Database a CoreTrustSeal certified repository. The database already meets several of the certification requirements, but not all. By integrating the database into the university's central research support, functions such as IT support, data curation, legal support, and e-archives will become more accessible to the repository and contribute to its development towards a more sustainable organization. One of the long-term goals of SND's collaborations is to create certified repositories at the HEIs in the SND network. The certification of Bolin Centre can serve as an example of how the process can proceed, and experiences from the project can be used to facilitate future certification initiatives.

National collaboration & projects

On a national level, SND collaborates with a wide range of stakeholders, such as Swedish HEIs, SUHF, the Swedish Research Council, the National Library, research infrastructures, national e-infrastructures, research funders, government agencies and other organizations within the Open Science landscape in Sweden.

Mistra Co Creating Better Blue (C2B2)

Launched in 2023, Mistra C2B2 is driving transformative change in Swedish ocean governance through participatory, data-informed co-creation. Within C2B2, SND supports marine researchers in improving data stewardship – offering help with data management plans, dataset preparation, and metadata documentation. This partnership aims to increase FAIR marine data and empower stakeholders to make decisions to create a sustainable, multisectoral blue economy. Learn more at c2b2.se.

The KAFFE¹ project – Mapping Capabilities within the E-infrastructure System for Research

The KAFFE project explores how researchers' data-related needs and practices align with existing e-infrastructures and how these systems can be developed to better identify and support future needs. It takes a comprehensive national view of research e-infrastructure – covering technical solutions, organizational structures, and human expertise – beyond just the remit of SND.

The project is divided into three tracks:

- **Track 1** analyzes eleven recent reports, surveys, and guidelines describing the current e-infrastructure landscape, drawing comparisons with research data studies from Swedish HEIs.
- **Track 2** investigates how key concepts are defined – or left undefined – in the same set of documents, highlighting communication challenges due to inconsistent terminology. This track also ensures that the capabilities used within the KAFFE project are clearly articulated.
- **Track 3** involves extensive interviews with researchers of varying levels of experience, across disciplines and institutions. Interview transcripts will be published after the project concludes.

Colleagues from HEIs and organizations within the SND Consortium and Network contribute actively to all tracks, led by the project team. Each track centres on enterprise architecture capabilities – the skills and structures needed to manage, preserve, and use research data within Swedish academia.

The project runs from November 2024 to November 2025.

¹ KAFFE = Kartläggning av Förmågor inom Forskningens E-infrastruktursystem

Researchdata.se

Researchdata.se is a collaborative effort to create a new national portal for finding and accessing research data and training materials on research data management. Participating infrastructures during the development phase, other than SND, are Bolin Centre for Climate Research, Huminfra, InfraVis, NBIS, SBDI/GBIF, SciLifeLab, SITES, and Swedigarch.

During 2024, the development of the portal has taken place in four working groups with participation from partners. These working groups have focused on different aspects of Researchdata.se: Sharing data; Metadata and harvesting; Education and training; and Design, communication, and outreach. These groups have been coordinated by a project management group.

The Researchdata.se platform will host research data and resources for research data management contributed by the project partners and will be a national portal primarily for Swedish researchers. SND's contributions to Researchdata.se include the research data catalogue and our popular "Manage data" web pages with information about how to manage and make research data accessible.

Researchdata.se is the largest deliverable during SND's current funding period with a launch date during the first quarter of 2025.

Snd.se

With the launch of Researchdata.se in March 2025, the SND website (snd.se) will be relaunched in an updated format. The website currently features a mix of instructional texts aimed at researchers, including general guidance on research data management (Manage data) and instructions on how to create data descriptions in DORIS for publication in SND's research data catalogue (Describe and share data). In contrast, materials aimed at DAU staff and research data support personnel is kept in a separate Wiki known as "the DAU Handbook."

In planning Researchdata.se, a decision was made to move the general guidance on research data management to the new portal. At the same time, content aimed at research data support staff from the DAU Handbook will be integrated into snd.se and made openly accessible. Instructional materials for researchers describing how to use DORIS will remain on snd.se. All texts are being revised and rewritten to ensure a consistent tone and structure.

User testing will be conducted with research data support staff from the SND network, and their feedback incorporated in the final versions of the materials.

Other content on snd.se – including information about the organization itself – will also be revised and updated.

Given the scope of work involved in launching Researchdata.se, not every element will be finalized by the launch in March 2025. The final structure will offer more clearly targeted content for each audience – both on snd.se and on Researchdata.se.

Training activities

Research data management training run by the organizations in the SND Network continues to develop and SND's involvement in training activities follows this trend. Whereas in 2023 SND staff visited network member organizations to give stand-alone presentations as part of the "SND pratar på plats" initiative, 2024 has seen a distinct shift towards SND staff participating in formal training programs organized by member organizations. Although these have been predominantly training programs for doctoral students – with the Swedish INterdisciplinary Graduate School in register-based research (SINGS) being perhaps the most high-profile – in 2024, SND has also participated in the Data Champions training program at Luleå University of Technology. Data Champions represent an emerging target group for research data training activities.

SND hosted two open webinars offering hands-on knowledge in research data management in 2024: "Hantera och dela intervjudata" (Managing and sharing interview data) in partnership with Umeå University, and "Qualitative data analysis software – Introduction to Nvivo" in partnership with Mälardalen University. The webinars were recorded and are available from [SND's YouTube channel](#).

SND has continued the successful formula of co-ordinating parallel training workshops in connection with our in-person SND network meetings. We greatly appreciate the contributions from our partners to the workshops on assessment of data access requests

(Halmstad University); geographic information systems (Stockholm University); and procedures for reviewing datasets (Swedish University of Agricultural Science, Stockholm University) och Luleå University of Technology). Other SND-run workshops covered digital tools for personal data risk assessment, and checksums for local file storage. The workshop "SND för nytilkomna" (SND for newcomers) is run in conjunction with every in-person network meeting to introduce new staff to SND and our work with open access to research data.

DiVA

In 2024, the transfer of datasets from DiVA – Academic Archive Online – to the Swedish National Data Service (SND) was completed, following discussions initiated the previous year. The data and associated metadata were published in SND's research data catalogue through the DORIS system.

Following the launch of Researchdata.se in March 2025, these datasets are accessible via the catalogue on Researchdata.se: [Datasets from DiVA](#).

International collaboration & projects

SND is part of a global network of research data infrastructures, where collaboration has a central role. SND's international collaborations fall into two main categories: initiatives from the European Union, such as EOSC and CESSDA ERIC, and organizations that provide essential services or expertise related to research data management and repositories.

EOSC

The vision for the [European Open Science Cloud](#), known as EOSC, is to put in place a system in Europe to find and access data and services for research and innovation. This is to help researchers store, share, process, analyze, and reuse FAIR research outputs within and across disciplines and borders. For these reasons, the EOSC Federation of nodes is being created, building on existing infrastructure and services supported by the European Commission, Member States and research communities.

The EOSC Association is the legal entity established to govern EOSC today, with 250 Members and Observers. SND, with the University of Gothenburg as host university, is a member, as well as 11 other Swedish organizations, including the SND Consortium universities.

With the establishment of the EOSC Federation, there will be a transition to a more stakeholder-driven approach with the goal of a shared vision, common objectives, and complementary contributions at European, national and institutional levels.

On a national level, there is a growing interest in EOSC. As EOSC increasingly enters an operational

phase, issues concerning its future governance and funding become more urgent topics for discussion. It is reasonable to assume that the technical and strategic development of EOSC will affect the Swedish research system, and it is a shared responsibility for the Swedish stakeholders of EOSC to ensure that there is preparedness and a common understanding of what we in Sweden want EOSC to be and develop into.

The Swedish Research Council organizes an annual national event on EOSC to enable strategic dialogue between university management, government agency leadership, research funders, and representatives from the Government Offices. SND contributes actively to this, as well as to the dialogue and development within the national coordination group for Swedish organizations that are members of the EOSC Association.

Skills4EOSC

[Skills4EOSC](#), a three-year project funded by Horizon Europe, was launched in September 2022. The project brings together expertise from national, regional, institutional, and thematic Open Science and Data Competence Centres from 18 European countries.

The goal of the project is to unify the current training landscape into a common and trusted pan-European ecosystem to accelerate the upskilling of European researchers and data professionals in the field of FAIR and Open Data, intensive-data science, and scientific data management.

In 2024, SND has continued to lead Work Package 8, “Synergies, stakeholder engagement, advocacy, and communications”, and take part in several other work packages and tasks. Other Swedish participants and affiliated entities are Chalmers University of Technology and Umeå University.

One of the key outputs of the project is the design and creation of a Competence Centre Network (CCNet). The initial steps for implementation have taken place in 2024 and it was putatively agreed that SND will be one of the inaugural competence centres, pending the signing of a memorandum of understanding. The idea is that these Centres will carry on implementing the Skills4EOSC project outputs even after the project has ended. The intention is for the CCNet to be a platform for collaboration and information exchange, and the mutual promotion of Open Science and information scientists in a collaboration that enables them to apply for international research funding as a single legal entity.

CESSDA ERIC

The [Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives](#) (CESSDA) is an ERIC, a European Research Infrastructure Consortium, which provides large-scale, integrated, and sustainable data services to the social sciences. It brings together social science data archives across Europe with the aim of promoting the results of social science research and supporting national and international research and cooperation. Sweden is a member of CESSDA ERIC and SND is appointed Swedish Service Provider.

DDI Alliance

The [Data Documentation Initiative Alliance](#) (DDI Alliance) is an international collaboration of member organizations that develops open metadata standards to enhance the quality, interoperability, and reusability of research data across social, economic, and health sciences. The alliance’s suite of metadata standards is used as base standards for the various systems developed by SND.

SND is a full member of the alliance and holds memberships in the alliance’s Executive Board, Controlled Vocabularies Working Group, DDI Developers Group and Technical Committee.

Statistics

The SND catalogue includes 2,938 entries published via DORIS.²
170 entries³ were added in 2024.

² As of 2024-12-31. Includes entries with at least one published, not withdrawn, version. Harvested entries are not included in this statistic.

³ Number of entries published as a first version during 2024.

Users

SND has 3,970 registered users.
There were 715 new registered users in 2024.

Catalogue page views

There were 151,429 views (or 136,971 unique views) of catalogue entries during 2024.

Downloaded material

There were in total 90,705 direct downloads⁴ from the catalogue in 2024.

Data requests

Many datasets that are not available for download can be requested from the SND catalogue. In 2024, SND received 562 requests, resulting in the dissemination of 998 datasets.

Data access level

Downloads

Access to data through SND – Data are freely accessible	46,677 (data and documentation)
Access to data through SND – Access to data is restricted/Data are accessible by request	35,804 (documentation only)
Access to data through an external actor	8,224 (documentation only)
TOTAL	90,705

⁴ Total number of downloads. Some downloads are comprised of several files. Attempts have been made to identify and remove automatic downloads by, for example, bots. It is, however, unlikely that they have been eliminated completely from the statistics.

Top 3 downloads

1

ACROBAT - a multi-stain breast cancer histological whole-slide-image data set from routine diagnostics for computational pathology.

**3,247
downloads**

2

Air pollution and noise GeoTIFF files for SCAPIS environment.

**2,912
downloads**

3

SCANIA Component X Dataset: A Real-World Multivariate Time Series Dataset for Predictive Maintenance.

**2,169
downloads**

Top 3 requested collections

1

The National SOM Survey

**636 dataset
requests**

2

Swedish Election Studies - Parliamentary Elections

**182 dataset
requests**

3

SVT Exit Poll Surveys

**80 dataset
requests**

Number of catalogue posts 1982–2024

During 2023, the SND catalogue was restructured to focus on datasets rather than studies with one or more datasets. This change has been applied retroactively to the years prior to 2023 in the chart.

Economy

Statement of financial performance for 2024

REVENUE	Results 2024	Budget 2024
Government grants	8,075	8,075
Sales	1,850	1,850
Internal funding	37	0
Co-funding	6,664	0
External research funding	21,515	20,175
Salary cost compensation from the SND Consortium	8,443	12,000
Financial gains	3	0
Accruals	-743	0
Depreciation coverage of grant-funded facilities	2	0
Total revenue	45,801	42,100
EXPENSES		
Salary costs	-21,211	-22,567
Salary costs for the SND Consortium	-8,443	-12,000
Holiday pay costs	-49	0
Other staff costs	-377	-535
Travel, representation, and PR expenses	-600	-835
Purchase of goods	-495	-380
Purchase of services	-2,931	-2,172
Indirect costs	-3,420	-3,420
Co-funding	-6,575	0
Premises	-1,549	-1,595
Financial costs	-4	0
Depreciation	-11	-20
Total expenses	-45,667	-43,525
Deficit/surplus for 2024	134	-1,425

Figures stated in thousand SEK.

Staff

SND office

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